

ANALYSING 'TWITTER CONVERSATION' OF LONDON TUBE STATIONS: THE CASE OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Covid-19 pandemic is deeply affecting urban mobility: the social-distancing strategies adopted to cope with the virus transmission pushed the majority of city users into avoiding public transport services in favour of safe and contactless travel options. To investigate this phenomenon, this paper proposes an Urban Informatics approach to understand passengers' opinions and expressed polarity through user-generated social-media data (Twitter) in the Greater London Area. The analysed corpus consists of 27,700 tweets posted between January 13rd, 2020 and May 17th, 2021, and geolocated in immediate proximity of a short sample of selected Tube Stations. Data was segmented in several phases, based on the restriction measures enforced by the UK National Authorities. Each subset is then analysed through texts structuring and semantic analyses, with LDA topic modelling and Sentiment Analysis. Finally, the outcomes of these processes are interpreted in their chronological succession and compared to demand data and service-disruption data.

1. INTRODUCTION

Urban Informatics (Foth et al., 2011) provides innovative assessment tools and metrics to support an effective planning of mobility services through an evidenced-based approach. Thanks to the recent development of advanced ICT solutions and the increasing availability of digitally widespread data sources, Big Data is becoming a valuable support to unveil hidden mobility patterns in cities (Batty, 2013; Crist et al., 2015).

Data is at the foundation of modern planning practice and among other tools that enable collection of mobility patterns and flows (Gorrini et al. 2021). In particular, user-generated social-media data has the potential to represent both national-scale (Jurdak et al., 2015) and urban-scale mobility patterns (Plunz et al., 2019). Thus these systems could contribute to the development of a comprehensive urban simulation model based on real-world data, to monitor, explain and simulate urban phenomena, widely referred to as Digital Twin (Fan et al., 2020).

Nowadays, this opportunity has become even more crucial considering the need to investigate the unprecedented effects of disruption of the Covid-19 pandemic on urban mobility. In particular, the nation-wide lockdown and post-lockdown phases have drastically changed citizens behaviours and mobility patterns related to the use of public transport services (Buhrmann et al., 2020), due to the need to avoid crowded transport infrastructures and public transport services in favour of safe and contactless travel options (e.g., private vehicles, cycling, walking, etc.).

In this context, the paper presents an extended analysis of a Twitter-data corpus, collected by geographical location and specific timeframes, and further filtered by removing non-relevant tweets and non-human posting. The acquired corpus consists of 27,700 tweets geolocated in immediate proximity of selected Tube Stations of the Greater London Area (UK) and posted between January 13rd, 2020 and May 17th, 2021. Given the analysis protracted timeframe, which encompasses both pre-pandemic weeks and diverse mobility-restrictions stages, the social-media data was segmented in No. 9 phases, selected in accordance with the evolution of the containment measures enforced by the UK National Authorities. This subdivision is the basis to compare the outcomes of the analyses in time-windows that have a mobility-demand significance, due to the increase (*or decrease*) of the restrictions, but also a social connotation, varying from strict lockdowns to milder social-distancing rules.

The current research aims to offer a comprehensive view of the relation between public transport and user-generated data; hence the proposed analysis is twofold. Firstly, the authors focused in understanding the impact of the pandemic on the public transport mobility patterns, through daily demand data and daily service-disruption data. Secondly, the social-media data is investigated with two different methodologies based on texts structuring and semantic analyses, specifically: (i) identification of tweets' subjects through LDA Topic Modelling, and (ii) assessment of the conversation emotional polarity through Sentiment Analysis.

The paper proposes a review of relevant applications of social-media data to assess mobility patterns, especially in relation with public transport systems, in order to provide a preliminary assessment of its advantages and limitations. Then, it presents the enabling data and methodology which sets the current work, and the results of time series analysis during the Covid-19 evolution. The paper concludes with final remarks about the achieved results, methodology limitations and future work.

1.1 Related Works

User-generated social-media data is used since the advent of large-scale internet communication to understand both social and mobility phenomena by evaluating the content and the associated metadata of posts. As a crowdsourcing information tool, Twitter was proven to be particularly effective since the introduction of the first Application Programming Interface (API) and has been used since as "Big Social Data" source (Burgess et al., 2012) and (McCormick et al., 2015).

Generally speaking, user-generated social-media data has proven to be an effective tool to investigate passengers' opinion, without the need to conduct cost-impacting and time-consuming surveys (Luong et al., 2015). In particular, Tweets' content can be accessed by geographical and semantic filter and it can be analysed to understand both long-term passengers' opinions as well as short-term trends, such as local service disruptions (Méndez et al., 2019).

In particular, the analysis of mobility patterns using Twitter data has been approached with diverse angles, both as a tool to understand individual mobility patterns by following the movements of specific users during a period of time (Osorio Arjona et al., 2020), and as a tool to understand system-wide mobility to further enrich the data with GIS data integration (Khan, 2020).

During the last year, many researchers focused on applying these methodologies to understand mobility in relation to Covid-19. By considering large-scale datasets geo-tagged tweets have been used to understand the general mobility patterns (Huang et al., 2020), and the relation with the virus transmission (Zeng et al., 2021), but also the opinion expressed in relation to vaccination (Hu et al., 2021).

2. ENABLING DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The data used in the research consists of two typologies of open-data: (i) authority-published data (i.e., Tube demand data) and (ii) user-generated data (i.e., tweets), which are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1 – List of datasets used in the research.

Data Typology	Dataset	Source	Comment
Authority-published	Covid-19 Restrictions Timeseries	GLA ¹	<i>Used to identify analysis phases</i>
	Transport for London Annual Counts for LU/LO/DLR/TfL Rail (by quarter hour)	TfL Open Data ²	<i>Used to select relevant Tube Stations</i>
	Number of Taps by Day and Station Type	TfL ³	<i>Used to assess daily demand in selected Tube Stations</i>
	Incident Data	TfL ⁴	<i>Used to assess service disruptions related to the selected Tube Stations</i>
User-generated	OpenStreetMap geo-data	OSM ⁵	
	Tweets' text and metadata	Twitter	<i>Retrieved using Twint Python package ⁶</i>

2.1 Analysis Timeframe and Stations' Selection

In accordance with the research scope, the phasing structure is derived from the evolution of the pandemic, specifically the phases were selected by considering the national and local policies imposing restrictions affecting London. The calendar, comprising of 25 policy milestones, was reduced to 9 phases in order to avoid an excessive segmentation of the outputs and by considering only the major self-distancing measure changes. In addition to the pandemic period, it was added a *Baseline Phase*, for the purpose of providing a reference scenario for the assessed indicators, this practice is common in before-after analysis and the timeframe chosen

was in line to the Coronavirus publications of TfL ³. The analysis timeframe is visible in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Phasing used in the analysis timeframe (red), derived from policies timeline enforced during pandemic period (light gray).

Similarly, a selection of Tube Stations was performed in order to identify the locations to look for geo-located tweets. This process was achieved by using demand data from 2019, published by TfL ², which represent the daily entry/exit for the typical weekday of a pre-pandemic year. The stations were selected by considering the 85th percentile of the demand, resulting in 40 stations located in the Greater London Area, see Figure 2 and 3.

Figure 2 – Stations average daily demand data (2019). The 85th percentile (28,440) is used as a reference value to select 40 relevant stations.

Figure 3 – Location of Tube Stations. The selected stations are highlighted and categorized by station typology as proposed by TfL³ data.

2.2 Tweets Corpora Definition

The selected stations' locations are used as centroids to calculate buffers of 400 meters of radius; the measure of the proposed catchment area around stations was chosen since it can be considered as a 5-minute walking distance in the analysis setting (Transport for London, 2010), moreover the small catchment area represent a location bias able to represent the content posted in proximity of public transport infrastructure. Therefore user-generated data is gathered by retrieving tweets posted in the immediate proximity of stations during the considered timeframe. The raw outcome of this process is a dataset comprising of 95,463 tweets, which was then post-processed in several step, in order to harmonize tweets' text to be input in further semantic analyses, removing noise and superfluous information.

The first step of this process was to detect repetitive and non-human posts in the overall corpus, which presence could lead to biased and inaccurate topic modelling, since automatically shared social media content express little or zero semantic information. After this step the number of tweets was reduced to 27,700, that is the extent of the corpus actually used in the analyses, see Figure 4.

Subsequently the text content of each post was pre-processed with characters-based simplifications removing punctuation signs, emojis, URLs and converting all the text to lowercase format. The cleaned text was then processed with Natural Language Processing (NLP) methodologies, such as stop words removal and lemmatizations (Bird et al., 2009). Both the two processes contribute to the harmonization of text and

the removal of words with no semantic meaning, enhancing the performance of the topic modelling, specifically: (i) stop words removal was based on the NLTK English stop-words list (e.g., a, an, the, etc.) (Birds et al., 2009), which was extended with custom words (e.g., London, etc.) that appeared ubiquitously in the corpus; (ii) lemmatization consists is a reduction of each word to its root and allows a further selection of allowed tokens; in this case, leading to the selection of nouns, verbs, adjectives and adverbs in each tweet. The data cleaning process was differentiated for topic modelling and sentiment analysis. The steps described above applies to the former, while the latter was not subjected to stop words removal, lemmatization and emojis removal, since emojis allow in-depth lexicon understanding.

Figure 4 – Timeseries of number of tweets per day: the cleaned corpora divided per phase (red) compared to the raw results (light gray).

2.3 Text Semantic Analysis

The two analyses performed to comprehend the content of the corpora were: (i) topic modelling, to gain knowledge on the main tweets’ subjects, and (ii) sentiment analysis, to investigate the expressed message polarity.

Topic Models are statistical language models used to understand the themes’ structure of a document. In particular, the used model was Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA), that is a probabilistic generative model which takes as input a collection of lemmatized texts and outputs topics’ probability distribution over each document (Kapadia, 2019). For each phase of the analysis timeframe, topic modelling was used to identify 10 topics per period. The model parameters were hyper tuned to obtain best fitting topics, looping over LDA’s main parameters. Subsequently, the significance of the results was quantified using the topics’ coherence metric, which measures the degree of semantic similarity between high scoring words in the topic, helping to

distinguish artifacts from semantically valid outcomes. In order to measure the influence of pandemic-related posts in the analysed corpora, a reference control set, built around Covid-19 related words, was defined and compared against the previously obtained topics. By using the reference set as an unseen document to query the models, the output was the probabilistic distribution of the queried control words among the phases' topics set.

Furthermore, Sentiment Analysis was performed using Vader (Valence Aware Dictionary and sEntiment Reasoner) (Hutto et al., 2014), a lexicon and rule-based analysis tool developed to estimate the polarity of social media texts. The tool outputs three values, defined as positive, neutral and negative scorings and a compound value to summarize the sentiment's results.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Demand Data Analysis

In addition to the demand used to select the stations, which was referred to the pre-pandemic year (2019), it was considered the daily demand of the selected timeframe, in order to understand the actual impact of Covid-19 on Tube's mobility. As shown in Figure 5 and Table 2, the variation between the phases is substantial, to the extent that during the last phase (P8) the average daily demand is -67% compared to the Baseline Phase.

Figure 5 – Timeseries of the total demand of the selected stations (red) compared with the percentage difference between the moving average, MA (time period: 3 days), and the cumulative average of values, CA. (light gray).

Table 2 – Demand of the selected stations divided by phase, with daily average and standard deviation. The table shows the percentage trends of the average daily demand between the phases and in comparison with the Baseline Phase.

Phases	Total	Average	SD	Trend (with previous)	Trend (with P0)
P0 - Baseline Phase	213,908,349	3,290,898	877,537	–	–
P1 - Lockdown 1	10,600,612	192,738	211,400	-94%	-94%
P2 - Transition Phase	80,119,943	635,873	320,281	+230%	-81%
P3 - Pre Lockdown 2	59,214,877	1,138,748	190,395	+79%	-65%
P4 - Lockdown 2	17,662,211	654,156	196,835	-43%	-80%
P5 - Tier 2 / Tier 3	19,625,099	1,090,283	282,439	+67%	-67%
P6 - Tier 4	5,371,465	335,717	130,154	-69%	-90%
P7 - Roadmap out of lockdown 1	50,677,574	522,449	170,902	+56%	-84%
P8 - Roadmap out of lockdown 2	37,764,241	1,078,978	180,895	+107%	-67%

3.2 Service Disruption Data Analysis

In order to structure a comprehensive view of the public transport usage during the pandemic’s evolution, the service disruption was taken into consideration. In this regard, the disruptions caused by diverse sources were categorized and aggregated per phase. The service interruption and delays were considered for all the Tube lines, since the selected stations are distributed among all the subway lines, and a service quality index was calculated in term of minutes of delay per day, shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 – Service quality index, expressed in minutes of delay per day, showing the major role of the Covid-19 related disruption (red).

3.3 Topic Modelling Analysis

Since the topic modelling analysis was performed on diverse corpora and the LDA model is generative, the reference was devised to infer the relation between Covid-19 related terms during the phases. The set consists in 17 terms, that also include variation of the same lemma, divided thematically in five categories:

- Pandemic: covid, corona, coronavirus, virus, pandemic;
- Lockdown: lockdown, quarantine, staysafe, stayhome;
- Prevention: distance, distancing, mask, facemask;
- Vaccine: vaccine, covidvaccine, vaccination;
- Other: nhs.

This set was built considering the overall corpus content by manually evaluating a random subset of tweets. The relative distribution of the reference set terms during the phases is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 – Graph showing the distribution of the reference set terms during the phases. The height of the curve is proportional to the number of tweets containing the relative term, divided by the number of tweets posted during the phase, so that the values are comparable among each other (categories' colours are the same of Figure 8).

The relation between the reference set and the phases' corpora is expressed by measuring how many terms of the set fall into the dominant topic (i.e., the topic with highest semantic similarity with the queried text) and the by the overall topic weight (i.e., the probability distribution of the topics in respect to the queried text). The output of this analysis is visible in Figure 8.

Figure 8 – Chart showing the weight of the dominant topic during the phases (black) and the reference set terms included in the dominant topic (coloured by category as in Figure 7).

3.4 Sentiment Analysis

Meanwhile the Topic Modelling Analysis is performed separately on each corpus, the Sentiment Analysis is used to interpret each single tweet, then the results are aggregated and interpreted per phase. VADER tool expresses the polarity of each item by three values, defined as positive, neutral and negative and a normalized weighted Compound Score to summarize the overall results (Hutto et al., 2014). For the scope of this research the value considered is the Compound Score, that expresses a single comparable score among the entries, shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9 – Chart showing the average Compound Score during the analysis timeframe (black) and the variation of the average Compound Score between phases (in gray the comparison with Baseline Phase and in red the comparison with the previous phase).

4. DISCUSSION

The use of user-generated social-media to understand public transport related mobility patterns can be performed with different methodologies. In this research, the authors’ choice was to consider a location-bias to gather the tweets data instead of using word-based selection criteria. The reason behind this choice was to be able to analyse content not only related to mass-transit utilization, and thus to be able to assess the general conversation topics and sentiment.

The analysed corpora, were significantly smaller than initially expected, however this is due to several reasons: (i) the geo-tagged tweets account to a small portion of the overall posted tweets (Huang et al. 2019), (ii) the search radius was knowingly small in order to enhance the effect of the location-bias, and (iii) given that the search location were the Tube stations, the Twitter activity was reduced consistently as the mobility demand. The general pattern that both demand data (Figure 5) and number of tweets (Figure 4) follow is predictable, and it appears as it is not directly related to the service quality index.

Meanwhile the demand and service data describe a currently well-known phenomenon, the text semantic analysis allows to gather more insights on the perception of the pandemic. As shown in Figure 7, the distribution of covid-related terms in the different phases allow to understand the evolution of the conversation: during the Lockdown 1 phase more focused on the actual situation, with the largest part of conversation focused on the “Pandemic” theme; followed by an interested more

related to the “Lockdown” theme and the restrictions measures, during Lockdown 2 phase; finally converged toward the “Vaccine” theme during the last analysed phases. By comparing these considerations to the topic modelling outputs, see Figure 8, it is possible to confirm some of these insights. During the Lockdown 1 phase (P1) the dominant topic relates to “Pandemic” and “Lockdown” themes and it shifts toward “Lockdown” in P4 and to “Vaccine” during the last phases. However, the Dominant topic weight metric shows how relevant is the topic in respect to the generated model. A more or less relevant topic can be influenced by several factors, such as an effective topic modelling process or the semantic significance of the analysed corpus, but for the scope of this research can be considered as a reference-set independent weight metric describing the relevance of the outputs.

Finally, the sentiment analysis can be interpreted using the threshold proposed by the tool creators (Hutto et al., 2014): typical compound limits are positive (score ≥ 0.05), neutral ($-0.05 > \text{score} > 0.05$) and negative (score ≥ -0.05). Considering these values, all the phases are characterized by a positive average compound score. However, social-media data is usually influenced by a positivity bias (Waterloo et al., 2018) because negative emotions are often considered as not appropriate to publicly share on social-media. For this reason, the trend metrics are proposed, and it is possible to appreciate how the general sentiment per phase is always lower than the Baseline Phase and especially how the variation closely follows the demand data, thus the restrictions implementation calendar.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The aim of the research was to approach the relation between Covid-19 pandemic and public transport in London using user-generated social-media data. The paper proposes a methodological approach aimed at comparing diverse metrics, ranging from demand and delay data to LDA topic modelling and sentiment analysis outputs. The analysis of social-media data, specifically, is steadily increasing its applications, ranging from sociological and medical studies to mobility related analyses. Therefore, crowdsourced data could be one the potential data feeds needed to develop a comprehensive model of an urbanized area (digital twin) able to describe and simulate phenomena happening in the urban environment, because other than location-based activity allows the comprehension of social-related patterns.

The results of the text semantic analyses performed in this research seem comparable to authority-published data. In particular, the number of tweets posted in the immediate proximity of Tube Stations follows the trend of the demand during the various phases and the evolution of the conversation analysed through LDA topic modelling is consistent with the results obtained from Sentiment Analysis. These two metrics describe the social aspect imposed by the restrictions, meanwhile the demand data and the service quality index describe the mobility aspect imposed by the same policies. Even if in a qualitative fashion, these sets of data manage to add information

otherwise difficultly obtainable, unless with the utilization of surveys or time-consuming and cost-impactive methods.

Future works will be based on improvements on both the data gathering techniques and text semantic analyses. The data acquisition of tweets' text and metadata could be done in real-time using the Twitter Streaming API, opening a range of possible applications, such as: (i) the investigation of specific time-related phenomena (e.g., delays and service disruptions), (ii) the mobility management for big-events (e.g., sports events and concerts).

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Notes

1. Source: https://data.london.gov.uk/download/covid-19-restrictions-timeseries/ae1b5b4c-3b5c-471f-b3e5-ba4fbc3eced9/restrictions_daily.csv
2. Source: http://crowding.data.tfl.gov.uk/Annual%20Station%20Counts/2019/ByQhrEntryExit_2019.xlsx
3. The daily demand dataset is available as part of the Coronavirus publications made available by TfL here: <https://tfl.gov.uk/corporate/publications-and-reports/coronavirus-publications> however the dataset was acquired by a Freedom of Information (FOI) request addressed to TfL, not done by the authors, available here: https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/updated_london_underground_stati_2
4. The daily delay dataset was acquired by a Freedom of Information (FOI) request address to TfL, done by the authors, available here: https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/london_underground_station_delay
5. Map data copyrighted OpenStreetMap contributors and available from <https://www.openstreetmap.org>
6. Twint is "an advanced Twitter scraping & OSINT tool written in Python that doesn't use Twitter's API, allowing you to scrape a user's followers, following, Tweets and more while evading most API limitations" available here: <https://github.com/twintproject/twint>